

EDUCATION FOR CHILDREN IN NEED OF SUPPORT IN KOKAND

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Abstract

This thesis examines the current state of education for children in need of support in Kokand City, Uzbekistan. It highlights the challenges faced by educators, parents, and the government in providing adequate educational opportunities for these children. The study evaluates the availability of resources, infrastructure, and community involvement in supporting children with disabilities. The research aims to offer practical recommendations for improving access to quality education for all children in Kokand, emphasizing the need for a more inclusive approach.

Keywords: special needs education, Kokand, disabilities, inclusive education, educational support, accessibility

Introduction

The education of children who need special support is a crucial aspect of creating an inclusive society. In Kokand City, various efforts have been made to integrate children with disabilities into the mainstream education system. However, several challenges persist, including inadequate facilities, lack of trained teachers, and societal stigma. This thesis seeks to provide an in-depth analysis of the current situation, exploring the resources available, the role of governmental and non-governmental organizations, and the perception of inclusive education within the community.

Limited Infrastructure: Schools in Kokand often lack the necessary facilities to accommodate children with disabilities. This includes ramps, accessible toilets, and learning aids tailored to their needs.

Insufficient Teacher Training: A significant challenge is the lack of specialized training for teachers. Educators struggle to adapt their teaching methods to cater to children with diverse needs, affecting the quality of education provided.

Societal Attitudes: Negative perceptions and lack of awareness within the community contribute to the exclusion of children with disabilities from mainstream education. There is a need for greater advocacy and awareness campaigns to change these attitudes.

National Educational Framework: The Uzbek government has implemented policies to promote inclusive education, but their impact in Kokand has been limited due to resource constraints.

Support from NGOs: Non-governmental organizations play a critical role in supplementing the efforts of the state by providing resources, training, and advocacy for children with disabilities.

Financial Challenges: The funding allocated for special needs education is often insufficient, limiting the availability of specialized learning tools, support staff, and therapeutic services.

4. Progress and Opportunities for Improvement

Inclusive Education Initiatives: Some schools in Kokand have started to adopt inclusive practices, such as integrated classrooms where children with and without disabilities learn together.

Community Engagement: Encouraging the involvement of parents, teachers, and local leaders has shown positive results in creating a more inclusive environment for children with special needs.

Future Directions: Recommendations for improving the education of children in need of support include better training for teachers, increased funding, and stronger partnerships between the government and NGOs.

Conclusion

The education of children in need of support in Kokand City remains a challenging yet critical issue. While there have been strides towards more inclusive education, significant gaps in resources, training, and societal attitudes remain. Addressing these challenges requires a coordinated approach involving educators, policymakers, and the community. With enhanced policies and greater community awareness, Kokand can create a more inclusive educational environment that supports all children, regardless of their needs.

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